

Deriving Equation to Account for the Effect of Added Electrolytes on the Viscosity of Sols of Colloidal Electrolytes

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Manuscript received 16 November 1976, revised 26 July 1977, accepted 3 October 1977

An equation has been deduced which can account quantitatively for the variation of the ratio, R, the specific viscosity of the sol containing added electrolyte to that of the original sol without any electrolyte, with the increase in concentration of the added electrolyte. The equation has been found to agree well with the data available in the literature on such systems as sols of agar, gum arabic, casein etc. with added electrolytes containing counter ions of different valency.

THE effect of addition, in small amounts, of strong electrolytes on the specific viscosity of a sol of a colloidal electrolyte of given concentration has been investigated by a number of authors¹⁻³. Such investigations have led them to the conclusion that a marked lowering of specific viscosity of the sol of a colloidal electrolyte occurs on addition of a strong electrolyte and that the counter ions and their valency are mainly responsible for the effect produced while the coions have practically no effect.

The aforesaid authors have qualitatively accounted for the observed effect with the help of Smoluchowski's extension of Einstein equation⁴ which may be written as follows

$$(\eta_s - \eta_o)/\eta_o = \eta_{sp} = k\phi \left[1 + \frac{1}{\eta_o a^2 \lambda} \left(\frac{D\xi}{2\pi} \right)^2 \right] \quad \dots(1)$$

where η_s represents the viscosity of the sol, η_o that of the dispersion medium, k, a constant which is 2.5 for spherical particles according to Einstein, ϕ , the volume fraction, ξ , the electrokinetic potential and a, the radius of the colloidal particles, D, the dielectric constant and λ the specific conductivity of the system.

When a strong electrolyte, in small quantity, is added to the sol, a, η_o and D remain constant but λ increases appreciably and ξ diminishes to some extent and hence the specific viscosity η_{sp} diminishes. At a given concentration of the added electrolyte as the valency of the counter ion increases, its capacity to reduce ξ and consequently the specific viscosity increases.

It will be shown in this paper that if R represents

† ξ represents the electro-kinetic potential and λ_i the specific conductivity of intermicellar liquid of the original sol before addition of any electrolyte. Therefore, each of them has got a fixed value. The assumption of linear variation of ξ and λ_i should hold good so long as S is small less than 20 millimoles.

the ratio of the specific viscosity of the sol containing an added electrolyte to that of the original sol without any added electrolyte, then the variation of R with the increase in concentration of the added electrolyte can be quantitatively accounted for by an equation deduced from theoretical consideration.

Derivation of the equation

It has been shown by the author⁵⁻⁷, in previous papers that the variation of specific conductivity of a sol of a colloidal electrolyte with dilution can be represented by the following equation :

$$\lambda = \theta\lambda_s + (1 - \theta)\lambda_i \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where θ is the fraction per unit area of the surface of electrode covered by the diffuse double layers of the colloidal particles and is equal to $C/(K_o + C)$ where C is the concentration of the colloidal electrolyte and K_o , a constant, λ_s is the specific conductivity of the diffuse double layer at the plane of contact with the electrode and λ_i the specific conductivity of the intermicellar solution.

Substituting the values of λ and θ in equation (1) it may be written as follows :

$$\eta_{sp} = k\phi \left[1 + \frac{(k_o + c)}{\eta_o a^2 (c\lambda_s + k_o\lambda_i)} \left(\frac{D\xi}{2\pi} \right)^2 \right] \quad \dots(3)$$

Let S be the concentration in milliequivalents per liter of the strong electrolyte added to the sol and let its effect in decreasing ξ and increasing λ_i be represented by $\xi(1 - bs)$ and $\lambda_i(1 + bs)$

respectively, then equation (3) may be written as follows :

$$\eta_{sp} = k\phi \left[1 + \frac{A\xi^2(1-bs)^2}{c\lambda_s + k_o\lambda_i(1+hs)} \right] \quad \dots(4)$$

where $A = \left(\frac{D}{2\pi}\right)^2 \frac{(c+k_o)}{\eta_o a^2}$, b and h are constants and S is small less than 20 millimoles per liter.

Denoting the specific viscosity of the sol with added electrolyte and that of the original sol without any added electrolyte by $(\eta_{sp})_s$ and $(\eta_{sp})_o$ respectively, we may by using equations (3) and (4) express their ratio, R as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} (\eta_{sp})_s : (\eta_{sp})_o = R &= \left[1 + \frac{A\xi^2(1-bs)^2}{c\lambda_s + k_o\lambda_i(1+hs)} \right] \\ &: \left[1 + \frac{A\xi^2}{c\lambda_s + k_o\lambda_i} \right] \\ &= \left[\frac{c\lambda_s + k_o\lambda_i(1+hs) + A\xi^2(1-bs)^2}{c\lambda_s + k_o\lambda_i + k_o\lambda_ihs} \times \right. \\ &\quad \left. \frac{c\lambda_s + k_o\lambda_i}{c\lambda_s + k_o\lambda_i + A\xi^2} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Now neglecting $(bs)^2$ as very small compared to the other terms, putting $B = (C\lambda_s + K_o\lambda_i + A\xi^2)$, and $H = (C\lambda_s + K_o\lambda_i)$ and simplifying the above expression, we may write as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} R &= \left[\frac{B - (2A\xi^2b - k_o\lambda_ih)s}{B} \times \frac{H}{H + k_o\lambda_ihs} \right] \\ &= \left[\frac{1 - (2A\xi^2b - k_o\lambda_ih)s/B}{1 + (k_o\lambda_ihs)/H} \right] \\ &= \left[1 - \frac{1 + (k_o\lambda_ihs)/H - 1 + (2A\xi^2b - k_o\lambda_ih)s/B}{\frac{k_o\lambda_ih}{H} \left(\frac{H}{k_o\lambda_ih} + S \right)} \right] \\ &= \left[1 - \frac{ms}{m_o + s} \right] \quad \dots(5) \end{aligned}$$

where $m = \left[\frac{(2A\xi^2b - k_o\lambda_ih)/B + (k_o\lambda_ih)/H}{k_o\lambda_ih/H} \right]$ and

$m_o = \frac{H}{k_o\lambda_ih}$ and all the terms in m and m_o are constants for a given added electrolyte.

In equation (5) S, represents the concentration of the counter ions in milliequivalents per liter. If the concentration is to be expressed in milligram ions per liter then equation (5) should be written as follows :

$$R = \left[1 - \frac{m(s/z)}{(m_o/z) + (s/z)} \right] \quad \dots(6)$$

where z represents the valency of the counter ions of the added electrolyte and (S/z) represents its concentration in milligram ions per liter.

It may be pointed out that in deducing equation (5), the radius, a has been assumed to remain constant. Therefore, it is not applicable to those cases where addition of an electrolyte changes the radius, a of the particle.

Notes on the data recorded in the tables :

Kruyt and Bungenberg de Jong¹ have measured the viscosity of purified agar sols (ash content 2.05%) at 50° in the absence as well as in the presence of electrolytes containing counter ions of different valency. Their data taken from the tables VI and VII of their paper¹ are recorded in the Tables I(a) to I(c). Column 2 of the tables, contains the

TABLE—1(a) VISCOSITY DATA OF AGAR SOL AT 50° WITH KCl

Experiment no.	Constants	S milli-equiv/L	η_s/η_o	R Observed	R Calculated
1	m = 0.309 m _o = 1.38	0	1.704	1.0	1.0
		0.05	1.698	0.992	0.989
		0.1	1.689	0.979	0.980
2	m = 0.309 m _o = 1.38	0	1.719	1.0	1.0
		1.0	1.617	0.858	0.870
		4.04	1.552	0.768	0.770
		10.1	1.515	0.716	0.728

TABLE—1(b) VISCOSITY OF AGAR SOL AT 50° WITH BaCl₂

Experiment no.	Constants	S milli-equiv/L	η_s/η_o	R Observed	R Calculated
1	m = 0.34 m _o = 0.62	0.0	1.704	1.00	1.00
		0.1	1.669	0.950	0.953
		0.2	1.638	0.906	0.917
		1.0	1.556	0.790	0.790
2	m = 0.34 m _o = 0.62	0.0	1.719	1.00	1.00
		2.0	1.537	0.747	0.740
		4.12	1.511	0.711	0.705
		8.08	1.492	0.684	0.684
		20.2	1.487	0.677	0.670

TABLE—1(c) VISCOSITY OF AGAR SOL AT 50° WITH Co(NH₃)₆Cl₃.

Experiment no.	Constants	S milli-equiv/L	η_s/η_o	R Observed	R Calculated
1	m = 0.373 m _o = 0.274	0.00	1.704	1.00	1.00
		0.045	1.673	0.956	0.947
		0.150	1.620	0.881	0.868
		0.300	1.571	0.811	0.805
		1.00	1.498	0.707	0.707
2	m = 0.373 m _o = 0.274	0.00	1.719	1.00	1.00
		1.50	1.499	0.694	0.685
		3.00	1.483	0.672	0.658
		6.00	1.471	0.655	0.643
		12.12	1.458	0.637	0.635
		30.30	1.453	0.630	0.630

values of the constants m and m_o in equation (5), column 3 contains the concentrations, S in milliequivalents per liter of the added electrolyte. The concentration, S of the electrolyte solution is so small that its viscosity is practically the same as that of water. In column 4 of the tables η_s and η_o

represent the viscosity of the sol and water respectively. R in the tables has the same significance as stated already.

The effect of strong electrolytes on the viscosity of positively and negatively charged casein sols has been investigated by Kruyt and Lier². The negatively charged casein sol has been prepared by peptising casein with NaOH. The pH of the sol is about 10.5 and further addition of alkali to it lowers its viscosity. The positively charged casein sol has been prepared by peptising casein with HCl and the pH of the sol is 2.75. According to the authors² the negatively charged casein sol becomes opalescent when it is treated with $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6\text{Cl}_3$ and the positively charged sol flocculates when it is treated with $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ or $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$. Therefore, equation (5) cannot be applied to these cases as the radius, a of the particles changes as S varies. The data of Kruyt and Lier² are recorded in the Tables 2 and 3. The terms S, η_s , η_0 and R have the same significance as stated already.

TABLE—2 VISCOSITY DATA OF NEGATIVELY CHARGED CASEIN SOL AT 50°

Electro-lyte used	Constants	S milli-equiv/L	η_s/η_0	R Observed	R Calculated
KCl	$m = 0.418$ $m_0 = 15.5$	0.0	1.279	1.0	1.0
		1.5	1.267	0.957	0.963
		4.0	1.255	0.914	0.914
		9.0	1.236	0.846	0.846
		15.0	1.226	0.810	0.795
BaCl ₂	$m = 0.735$ $m_0 = 12.7$	0.0	1.279	1.0	1.0
		1.5	1.261	0.936	0.946
		4.0	1.230	0.824	0.824
		9.0	1.190	0.682	0.695
		15.0	1.168	0.602	0.602

TABLE—3 VISCOSITY DATA OF POSITIVELY CHARGED CASEIN SOL AT 50°

Electro-lyte used	Constants	S milli-equiv/L	η_s/η_0	R Observed	R Calculated
BaCl ₂	$m = 0.345$ $m_0 = 5.73$	0.0	1.285	1.0	1.0
		1.5	1.264	0.926	0.928
		3.25	1.248	0.870	0.875
		7.00	1.229	0.804	0.811
		13.00	1.213	0.747	0.761
K ₂ SO ₄	$m = 0.45$ $m_0 = 1.71$	0.0	1.285	1.0	1.0
		0.75	1.246	0.863	0.863
		1.50	1.225	0.790	0.790
		3.25	1.196	0.688	0.701
		7.00	1.182	0.639	0.639

In the Tables 4(a) to 4(d) are recorded the data of Kruyt and Tendeloo³ on the viscosity of gum arabic sols collected from the tables V, VII and VIII of their papers. The terms, S, η_s , η_0 and R have the same significance as stated already.

The data, with reference to equation (6), are recorded in Table 5. Columns 3 and 4 of the table contain the values of the constants m and (m_0/z). In column 5, (S/Z) represents the concentration in

milligram ions per liter and the other terms have the same significance as stated already.

TABLE—4(a) VISCOSITY DATA OF GUM ARABIC SOL AT 25°

Electro-lyte used	Constants	S milli-equiv/L	η_s/η_0	R Observed	R Calculated
KCl	$m = 0.663$ $m_0 = 1.45$	0.00	1.528	1.00	1.00
		0.50	1.438	0.830	0.830
		1.00	1.386	0.731	0.729
		5.00	1.257	0.487	0.486
NaCl	$m = 0.663$ $m_0 = 1.45$	0.00	1.528	1.00	1.00
		0.50	1.438	0.830	0.830
		1.00	1.385	0.729	0.729
		5.00	1.257	0.487	0.486
LiCl	$m = 0.663$ $m_0 = 1.45$	0.00	1.528	1.00	1.00
		0.50	1.438	0.830	0.830
		1.00	1.386	0.731	0.729
		5.00	1.258	0.490	0.486

TABLE—4(b) VISCOSITY DATA OF GUM ARABIC SOL AT 25°

Electro-lyte used	Constants	S milli-equiv/L	η_s/η_0	R Observed	R Calculated
BaCl ₂	$m = 0.745$ $m_0 = 0.98$	0.00	1.532	1.00	1.00
		0.5	1.405	0.761	0.748
		1.0	1.330	0.620	0.624
		5.0	1.200	0.376	0.377
SrCl ₂	$m = 0.745$ $m_0 = 0.98$	0.00	1.532	1.0	1.0
		0.50	1.405	0.761	0.748
		1.00	1.330	0.620	0.624
		5.00	1.200	0.376	0.377
MgSO ₄	$m = 0.745$ $m_0 = 0.98$	0.00	1.532	1.00	1.00
		0.50	1.403	0.758	0.748
		1.00	1.330	0.620	0.624
		5.00	1.201	0.378	0.377

TABLE—4(c) VISCOSITY DATA OF GUM ARABIC SOL AT 25°

Electro-lyte used	Constants	S milli-equiv/L	η_s/η_0	R Observed	R Calculated
La(NO ₃) ₃	$m = 0.882$ $m_0 = 1.25$	0.00	1.543	1.00	1.00
		0.50	1.406	0.748	0.748
		1.00	1.330	0.609	0.608
		5.00	1.157	0.289	0.294
Co(NH ₃) ₆ Cl ₃	$m = 0.882$ $m_0 = 1.25$	0.00	1.543	1.00	1.00
		0.50	1.406	0.748	0.748
		1.00	1.323	0.595	0.608
		5.00	1.160	0.295	0.294

TABLE—4(d) VISCOSITY DATA OF GUM ARABIC SOL AT 25°

Electro-lyte used	Constants	S milli-equiv/L	η_s/η_0	R Observed	R Calculated
*Pt(en) ₃ (NO ₃) ₄	$m = 1.03$ $m_0 = 1.46$	0.00	1.527	1.00	1.00
		0.50	1.385	0.730	0.737
		1.00	1.306	0.581	0.582
		2.50	1.193	0.366	0.350
		5.00	1.105	0.192	0.203

* Pt(En)₃(NO₃)₄, Here En stands for ethylenediamine

Discussion

In column 6 of the tables 1(a) to 4(d) are recorded the values of R calculated by using equation (5). It will be noticed that the calculated values of R agree well with those observed for the sols referred to in the aforesaid tables. It will also be noticed from the data recorded in the aforesaid tables that the ability of the counter ions, at a given

TABLE—5 VISCOSITY WITH REFERENCE TO EQUATION (6)

Colloid	Electrolyte used	Values of		S/Z miligram ions/L.	η^s/η_0	R	
		m	m_0/Z			Observed	Calculated
Agar sole at 50°C	KCl	0.309	1.38	0.00	1.719	1.00	1.00
	"	"	"	1.00	1.617	0.858	0.870
	BaCl ₂	0.34	0.31	4.04	1.552	0.768	0.770
	"	"	"	1.00	1.537	0.747	0.740
	Co(NH ₃) ₆ Cl ₃	0.373	0.091	4.04	1.492	0.684	0.684
	"	"	"	1.00	1.483	0.672	0.658
Gum arabic sole at 25°C	KCl	0.663	1.45	4.04	1.458	0.637	0.635
	"	"	"	0.00	1.528	1.00	1.00
	BaCl ₂	0.745	0.49	5.00	1.257	0.487	0.486
	"	"	"	0.00	1.532	1.00	1.00
	Co(NH ₃) ₆ Cl ₃	0.882	0.417	2.50	1.200	0.376	0.377
	"	"	"	0.00	1.543	1.00	1.00
"	"	"	"	1.67	1.160	0.295	0.294

increases. In agreement with this observation the concentration, to reduce R increases as their valency value of m in equation (5) increases as the valency of the counter ions increases.

From the data recorded in Table 5 it may be concluded that the constant (m_0/Z) in equation (b) diminishes as the valency of the counter ion increases. It indicates, that the ability of the counter ions to increase the specific conductivity of the intermicellar solution, increases as their valency increases.

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